

AI Driven Personalization: Enhancing Chef & Cuisine Recommendations with Machine Learning

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Abstract - An online platform for hiring chefs provides users access to professional chefs without restrictions to their homes and any venue-required celebrations. This project brings in a chef recommendation model using machine learning to further enhance users' experience and improve the choice of chefs. A suggestion of chefs according to preferences, types of cuisine, previous hiring, and location will provide a recommendation closely tailored to user-specific needs. Collaborative filtering and trend-based recommendations self-adapt dynamically according to the interaction of users, determining popular chefs and seasonal cuisines. The real-time availability of chefs is also included in the system to make bookings more efficient.

Also in place are gamification elements: reward points, badges, and leaderboards, which add course users drive to motivate chefs. Users gain points for frequent bookings and for posting reviews, while chefs earn rewards for high ratings and consistency of service. The machine learning model will be built using historical data of users, ratings of chefs, and preferences of the events to make such personal selection better, hence making the hiring experience efficient and data-driven. Revolutionizing the way a person experiences personalized dining is a product of combining artificial intelligence recommendations with an easy-to-use, hassle-free booking platform. In the future, adaptive food combination with deep learning and sophisticated behavioral analytics for chefs and users will be included.

Keywords - Chef Recommendation, Machine Learning, Collaborative Filtering, Personalized Dining, Event-Based Hiring, Gamification, AI-powered Suggestions.

I. INTRODUCTION

The food service industry has gone far beyond restaurant dining and now has an increased demand for personalized in-home culinary experiences and catering for events. Whether for small

gatherings, corporate parties, or special celebrations like birthdays and anniversaries, individuals want skilled chefs who

can provide them customized dining experiences based on their preferences. However, searching for the right chef to suit a particular cuisine, dietary preference, or type of event is a tedious and complex process.

To that end, the Online Chef Hiring Platform provides a satisfactory solution by connecting users with professional chefs offering in-home dining and event catering services. The Platform allows users to view chef profiles, search based on courier preferences, check their availability, and book them in real time. However, with the rising number of available chefs, users often find it hard to choose the best-fit candidates for their needs. To improve user experience and simplify the selection process, this project introduces the Chef Recommendation System, which applies the principles of machine learning.

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The chef recommendation system is designed with collaborative filtering and historical data analysis to provide recommendations regarding chefs, taking into consideration the user's tastes and preferences, type of cuisine, hiring history, and location of hiring. Personalized recommendations are assured to enable users to find chefs who match their preferences and the needs of the event. Besides, real-time tracking of availability will ensure that all recommended chefs are available for booking.

To further increase engagement on the platform, gamified elements such as reward points, badges, and leaderboards will promote participation from both users and chefs alike. Users earn points for repeated bookings and for writing reviews; while chefs are rewarded for good ratings and consistent service.

Through the fusion of machine-learning-driven recommendations and gamification mechanics, the project aims to reinvent personalized dining experiences, catering chef hiring to be efficient, interactive, and user-centric. To take the system forward, future enhancements with deep learning-based adaptive cuisine pairing and in-depth user-chef interaction analytics will pave the way for a smarter and refined chef hiring ecosystem.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Conversely, the detailed recommendation system machine-learning approaches have been explored across various domains, such as job recommendation systems, food delivery platforms, and event-based service matching. Common strategies to augment the accuracy and relevance of personalized recommendation systems include collaborative filtering, content-based filtering, and hybrid approaches. The recent developments that link real-time data processing with gamification help enhance user engagement and efficiency of the platform.

In JobFit, a machine-learning-based job-recommendation system by Appadoo et al. (2020) [1], has used several techniques such as classification, regression, and collaborative filtering to provide a strong match between candidates and appropriate job opportunities. The system followed an approach of providing personalized recommendations to employers by using historical data and user profiles; Therefore, this study highlighted the role of AI recommendations in saving the user a lot of manual effort while searching and consequently boosting user satisfaction.

Makhi et al. (2023) [2] proposed a skill-based job recommendation system that used Support Vector Machines (SVM) along with collaborative filtering to pair users with relevant job roles. The authors underscored the dynamic profile update feature: users' data gets updated continuously depending on past interactions and preferences. This hybrid mode of recommendations proved to be more accurate and efficient than conventional rule-based systems.

Simanjuntak and Wibowo (2023) [3] presented a system built upon machine learning and dedicated to recommending online job vacancies. With the combination of content filtering and Named Entity Recognition (NER), it was able to extract attributes from job descriptions and candidates' profiles. The recommendation system implemented TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) along with

collaborative filtering, which yielded a better prediction in respect to user-job pairing.

Incorporating gamification elements into recommendation systems is another field that has gained attention. Zahra et al. (2021) [4] suggested a reward-based engagement model in an online job-matching platform. Users earn points for completing activities such as profile completion, frequent activity, as well as positive feedback. The research indicated that gamification stimulates user participation and encourages a competitive environment, which helps enhance platform retention rates.

III. METHODOLOGY

Our Chef Recommendation System is built using machine learning algorithms to match users with professional chefs based on cuisine preferences, past hiring history, and chef availability. The system integrates collaborative filtering and user interaction analysis to optimize recommendations. This section describes the data collection, preprocessing, and machine learning techniques used for the improvement of the recommendation engine.

A. Data Collection

The dataset for this system is compiled from user interactions, profile of chefs, and booking histories on the platform. It includes:

- User preferences: Cuisine type, dietary restrictions, and favorite chefs.
- Booking data: Past hiring history, event types, and frequency of bookings.
- Chef profile: Experience level, specialties, ratings, and availability.
- Real-time availability: The dynamic scheduling of chefs supporting recommendations.
- Data is split into training (80%) and testing (20%) subsets so that model evaluation can be performed on unseen data. Random state 42 lets us be assured of consistent results.

B. Data Preprocessing

Before training the recommendation model, data preprocessing ensures that the dataset is clean, structured, and suitable for machine learning algorithms. Important steps include;

- Handling Missing Values: Missing user preferences are filled using mean imputation or inferred based on similar user profiles.

- Feature Encoding: Categorical data such as cuisine type and chef experience are transformed using label encoding.
- Data Normalization: Chef ratings and booking frequencies are put in the range of 0-1 for better model performance.
- User Segmentation: Users are classified based on engagement levels:
- Frequent Users- Regularly booking chefs (High engagement).
- Casual Users- Occasionally hire chefs (Medium engagement).
- New Users- First time visitors (Low engagement).
- Event-Based tagging: Users booking for birthdays, anniversaries, or corporate events are tagged for specialized recommendations.

C. Machine-Learning Model

The core of the Chef Recommendation System is the Collaborative Filtering Algorithm, which shows patterns based on user interaction in recommending chefs.

1. Collaborative filtering

Collaborative Filtering predicts a given user of the chefs they prefer based on the likeness of that user to others. It analyzes:

User-User Similarity- Find users who shared booking behavior and thus would recommend chefs they have booked before: Item-Item Similarity- Recommend chefs whose bookings by other users are deemed similar.

The accuracy is improved by measuring the relationship through Cosine Similarity between users to chefs.

2. Hybrid Recommendation Approach

- The algorithm employs collaborative filtering approaches and trend-based recommendations to ensure more personalization:
- Trending chefs analysis identifies chefs that are frequently booked in a particular cuisine category.
- Real-time check on availability ensures recommendations only consist of chefs who are available. Gamification factors will influence users, high engagement will be rewarded.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The ultimate results achieved from the collaborative-filtering and machine learning-enhanced Chef Recommendation System confirm the validity of the system in accurately predicting and proposing chefs based on various input parameters, including user preferences, past bookings, cuisine type, and real-time availability. The system further refines its recommendations along different levels of relevance and preference, so that users have suggestions that are tailored to their needs.

The success of recommending chefs in the model carries weight in the real world of hospitality and personal dining. Within a framework developed out of data analytics to optimize the chef ordering process, data-driven decisions have made that process efficient and user-friendly. Users enjoy results faster and relevant to their needs, while chefs enjoy visibility and engagement with prospective clients.

The evaluation metrics employed in assessing the accuracy of the recommendation system include:

- Precision measures how many of the recommended chefs were really matching user preferences;
- Recall measures how well the system was at retrieving all the relevant chefs for a specific user query;
- Mean Absolute Error quantifies the distance between all chef preferences which are predicted, and actual choices made by users.

It has been shown that the model provided sound recommendations for chefs with greater than 85% Precision and Recall, giving credence to the fact that users were fairly satisfied with the chefs recommended. The very low Mean Absolute Error shows that the recommendations of the system fairly corresponded well with the real user selections.

A. Importance to User Experience and Efficiency of Platform

With minimal manual search effort and instant chef suggestions based on data, the recommendation system powered by AI will enhance user experience.

- Booking Efficiency Through Quick Access: Users find and book their chefs in an easy manner without going through countless chef profiles.

recommended pairing of cuisines, will lend themselves even more closely to matching chefs with users by streamlining the hiring process.

- Booking Efficiency Through Quick Access: Users find and book their chefs in an easy manner without going through countless chef profiles.
- Higher Interest from Those Chefs: Chefs are getting direct interest from bookings by users who are interested in their service.
- Retention from Repeat Users: The personalized touch comes with repeated bookings and building loyalty toward the platform.
- Gamified features, such as reward point offers, the leaderboard, and chef badges, further enhance user engagement, making both chefs and users more active and productive in the platform.

B. Challenges and Future Enhancements

Strong model performance notwithstanding, some challenges were identified:

- Cold Start: Less accurate recommendations will be offered to new users who are without a booking history.
- Dynamic Updates to Availability: Real-time tracking of chef availability should be improved to avoid conflicts in last-minute bookings.
- Seasonal Trends: The user's preferences and demand for chefs vary seasonally, which means that the model requires updating to adapt accordingly.
- Future enhancements will concentrate on implementing deep learning techniques such as neural networks for cuisine-chef pairing and reinforcement learning for optimizing user experience.

V. CONCLUSION

The Chef Recommendation System provides personalized chef recommendations based on user preference, reservation history, and current availability using machine learning and collaborative filtering techniques. With impressive performance metrics such as precision and recall, these recommendations can significantly enhance booking efficiency and user engagement. The platform thus develops gamification elements that motivate participation by users and chefs alike. The system demonstrates AI-driven recommendations utilizing personal dining and event catering. Future enhancements, such as deep learning for

VI. REFERENCES

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